

Scholarship of Teaching and Learning (SoTL) Portfolio: Experience, Research, and Inquiry for Teaching Excellence in Higher Education

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Abstract

This study is a collection of responses created from experience, research and inquiry into teaching and learning practices in higher education. The research initializes with teachers learning to teach and enquires about planning and designing curriculum, assessments, feedback, collaborative learning and mentorship. The study advances towards leadership in higher education teaching and evaluates the universal design of learning, scholarship of teaching and learning (SoTL), quality of learning and teaching programs and teaching excellence endeavours. The author has collected data for this research from personal experience, peer practices, scholarly and professional literature, and inquiry into the constituents of the concepts. As the study progresses, the reflections from experiences and research have turned to certain propositions and conceptual framing. The study limits to reflections and evaluations of self and peers' experiences and practices. However, the implications are not limited to higher education. The inquiry into the higher education SoTL for creating teaching excellence pursuits extends its impacts into professional development and adult education in non-academic settings.

Keywords: Higher Education, SoTL, Teaching, Learning

Key Learning Principles

I would discuss two of the principles:

Principle: Facilitates the development of self-assessment (reflection) in learning

Practice to enhance students' learning experience:

- Opportunity of self-evaluation of drafts with constructive feedback.
- Guidance to explore more resources to improve reflection and critical evaluation.
- Develop knowledgebase with self-questioning and self-prompting.

Assistance in learning and students feeling.

- Confidence development for self-evaluation and improvement.

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- Self-learning capabilities development
- Motivational approach to achieve learning outcomes.

Principle: Provides information to teachers that can be used to help shape the teaching

Practice to enhance students learning experience:

- Sharing information on students' *self-evaluation capabilities*
- Data and information on students' self-design of activities and outcomes achieved.
- Reinforcement strategies to enhance students learning outcomes.
- Operationalized action plan to achieve the outcomes.

Assistance in learning and students feeling:

- Building strategies on existing knowledge about students' capabilities
- Extended action plan to support students' learning experience.
- Nurturing students' confidence, motivation, and trust

Institutional policies on the use of seven principles, feedback, and feed forward concept:

The institution uses these seven principles in the following communications:

- Organisation policies
- Communications with peers and stakeholders
- Communications with students and faculty in learning management system
- University handbooks'

Incorporation of seven principles in my unit/course:

I consider that I can incorporate these seven principles in the accounting and finance units in the following manner.

- Facilitate research-based learning approach.
- Demonstrate real-life accounting scenarios.
- Simulate accounting scenarios and cases.
- Encourage critical evaluation and suggestive responses.
- Encourage self-evaluation of drafts or activities.
- Provide constructive feedback to learners for operationalized knowledge building.
- Engage peer assessment and reviews.
- Sharing strategies and action plan with peers in my cohort
- Sharing the actionable strategies with wider community through my own teaching experience

In the discussion board below, post three belief statements representing what you value most in learning and teaching.

Refer back to the concept map you prepared in Activity 2 to refine your belief statements. You will need to **connect** and **synthesise** ideas that are thematically represented in your concept map.

Aim for clarity and concision and supply your top three beliefs only.

I value these three notions as the belief statements in learning and teaching: clarity, collaboration, and evidence. In this context, I consider that clarity of concepts for students and peers improves collaboration to generate evidence of teaching and learning outcomes. These

three belief statements are three pillars on which one can formulate a learning and teaching pitch. Clarity of ideas enhances collaboration amongst student-teacher, teacher-teacher, and student-student relations. Once they improve collaborative environment and are on the same page, they can generate the evidence that is applicable and generalizable within the academic environment.

Following are the three case scenarios to understand the connection amongst the three belief statements.

1. If a student understands the teacher's feedback, he can relate the response to feedback, thus improves understanding in their relation.
2. When a student delivers this feedback with clarity to peers, he develops enhanced collaborative environment with peers.
3. Teachers can share ideas with clarity that encompasses operationalization of strategies and concepts. This is how they can relay the compatible communication amongst peers.

This is notable that these strategies can enhance the collaboration to achieve evidence-based outcomes. In addition, this succinct approach relies on circular effect of these belief statements. Nonetheless, evidence initiate from clear collaborative thoughts in turn leads to opportunities of clear ideas and further collaborations to enhance evidence of learning and teaching outcomes. However, I would say that the applicability of these beliefs on different concepts and settings needs evaluation to build arguments and adhere to my philosophy.

Search your institution's website and identify one example of a professional development activity or a resource that is available to support you with good teaching.

Post a one-sentence description of the professional development activity or resource, together with the URL if the webpage is publicly available, i.e. not password protected.

The institution has a range of training activities for staff that includes workshops, seminars and professional development courses. However, I preferred learning qualitative and quantitative data analysis and modelling techniques and tools. For example, the institutions' focus on NVIVO, SPSS and Stata were quite beneficial for my own research. I also had research development and writing workshops to enhance my academic writing capabilities. Although, those were for knowledge and practice, I could later utilize skills to teach. In addition, institution arranges faculty workshops and seminars to develop collaborative environment and provide learning opportunities.

The [module notes](#)

[Download module notes](#) provide six definitions of reflection (numbered 1-6).

What definition is your favourite?

Post the number of the reflection definition that resonates best with you. Provide a sentence to explain why you have chosen this definition.

I consider these three definitions for logical reasoning on reflection.

Definition 1. A deliberate and conscientious process that employs a person's cognitive, emotional, and somatic capacities to mindfully contemplate on past, present, or future (intended or planned) actions to learn, better understand, and potentially improve future actions (Harvey, Coulson & McMaugh, 2016, p. 9).

Response: In this definition, author has contemplated senses, feelings within thought process for developing an action plan. This contemplation can lead to improvements.

Definition 2. Deliberately thinking about action with a view to its improvement (Hatton & Smith, 1995, p.34)

Response: This definition presents the solution-oriented aspect of the thought process that adds value. However, where the thought process to identify solutions is coming from is missing in this definition.

Definition 3. Reflection helps students make stronger connections between theoretical perspectives and practice. We view reflection as a skill that can assist students in making sense of their service-learning experience (Correia & Bleicher, 2008, p.41).

Response: The definition connects theory and practice from students' perspective. Authors affirms reflection as skills that informs to practice.

Conclusively, I would say, that either of these definitions is the authors' argument. However, the emerging research can seek benefits of learning through these definitions and developing stronger arguments to inform theory and practice.

Module 8: Activity 2. Share a reflective prompt

Post a link to an item you think you may use as a prompt for reflection for learning.

You could search for a link to a video, an image, audio or some text.

Activity 9-3

After watching the video on the previous page, consider the following four approaches to university teaching. Use your knowledge of the human brain to reflect on each approach.

When you are ready, post in the discussion forum about why this approach will or will not be effective, and why.

1. You are designing a new university course. You want to make the course more interesting for students, so you have built in fancy transitions on lecture and tutorial slides and chosen a number of different fonts. In your learning management system, you have replicated these fonts. You find your standard institutional template quite boring, so you have shuffled the content around.

Response: Cognitive load may not help students to interact with fancy transitions and numerous fonts. They can face the challenges such as:

- information processing
- focus on the core theme
- comprehension
- critical evaluation
- synthesis of information
- time management

Additional Response to address challenges: In this context, the course designer can keep the subject matter interesting while keeping the existing template or adaptable modifications. For example,

- Designing the course with visuals and narrate with text
- Tabular and matrix approach
- Variation of font sizes
- Transitions with chapter or section highlights
- Link building to jump to sections

2. You are designing a new university course. You know practice supports learning, so you give students the textbook to read and ask them to repeat this process several times.

Response: In my opinion, repeated reading has its own benefits. Every time students can find something interesting in the book. However, repeated reading should have a focused approach. Being an instructor, I can develop the following strategies to enhance students learning from the same content over time in a repeated fashion.

- Categorize the book chapters into topics.
- Relate the topics from different chapters
- Ask to complete exercises and activities relevant to the topics from each chapter
- Identify sub-topics within the topics to deepen students understanding
- Relate the Sub-topics within chapter and amongst different chapters
- Ask students to complete exercises and activities relevant to the sub-topics.

In my opinion, repeated reading with focused approach can open new avenues in the same content. The focused strategy can assist students to

- Deepen their understanding of the themes and sub-themes
- Get along with the content and know the language of the concepts
- Evaluate the content with more critical perspective
- Synthesize the information with in-depth knowledge of the content
- Reflect and create the new content

3. You are designing a new university course. You are covering a big area with lots of interesting developments, so you have tried to squeeze as much in as possible. Although the pace of your classes is fast, you have also given lots of information about extension topics. You hope students will become passionate about the subject.

Response: In my opinion, lots of information differs from lots of content. This is notable whether I deliver information for the same topic or multiple topics.

Case 1: If I squeeze multiple topics with lots of information, it can build a cognitive load. The students will face the following challenges to process information under multiple topics.

- Thinking about each topic and related information individually.
- Preparation and focus on more important topics to pass the exam and assessments.
- Time management constraints to prepare each topic
- Grasping the topic fully to analyse and synthesize
- Ability to build their opinion about the topic

Case 2: If I add more information under core topics and beginners' information in extension topics, the students can enjoy comparative advantage in the following manner.

- Focus on the core topics for study, discussions and examinations
- Deepen their understanding of the core themes with additional information.
- Relate the core themes to extended development topics
- Develop interest and discussions around extension topics
- Build new hypothesis from core themes while thinking around extension topics

4. You are designing a new university course. You want to stimulate higher-order thinking, so you do away with the knowledge-building activities that your predecessor left you and move straight into analysis. You hope students might develop any knowledge and skills they need along the way.

In my opinion, analysis without knowledge building is just like jumping into the swimming pool without knowing how to swim. Therefore, knowledge building from predecessors contributes. I would align my discussion around two cases in the scenario of directly prompting students to initiate analysis.

Case 1: Students prompted to initiate analysis without prior knowledge for brainstorming and initial hypotheation purpose.

In this case, following opportunities and challenges exist.

Opportunities:

- Identify students understanding of the topic
- Evaluate students' cognitive capabilities
- Understand their capabilities to get along with the topic
- Identify the potential to improve course design

Challenges:

- Disengagement to get along with the new topic
- Students overwhelming situation due to cognitive burden
- Instructor's overrated bias of students' cognitive capabilities
- Bottle-neck to cognition and reversal to the existing learning mode

Case 2: Students prompted to conduct analysis without prior knowledge for developing new knowledge and outcomes.

This case recognizes the following opportunities and challenges

- Development of new knowledge from students' interactive cognitions with the environment
- Relation of new knowledge with prior knowledge due to cognitive similarity and exposure to similar environment over generations
- Addressing current challenges while conducting analysis

Challenges:

Cognitive load to brainstorm, hypothesize and advent or invent without any existing knowledge support, analogous to jumping in ocean for swimming without any knowledge of swimming.

- No relevance to the prior knowledge in context of cognitive process of predecessors
- Spurious outcomes in case of no prior consultation
- Vicious circle of problems without learning the best practices of predecessors
- No opportunity of the synthesis and critical evaluation of the prior knowledge and practices of predecessors.

Module 9: Understanding learning: Activity 2

In the previous video, we talked about how (and why) active learning strategies are beneficial.

In this activity, think about a topic you know or have taught before. Design a simple active learning exercise for students that is going to be optimal for their learning. Remember the principles of encoding and retrieval!

Post in the discussion board below to share your active learning exercise.

I would select one accounting concept to review here for optimal students learning.

Topic 1: Accounting Principles

Application of Encoding Principles:

1. **Chunking:** The topic comprises few principles that need individual focus therefore, I would prefer making sub-sections.
2. **Organisation:** Organisation of sub-sections from easy to difficult level can enhance the student's level of understanding from shallow to deeper encoding level.
3. **Repetition:** I consider the recap of the sub-section and the whole section for memorization.
4. **Mnemonics:** Analogical examples can support students learning so I would offer real-world examples for this purpose.
5. **Multimodal presentations:** The topic needs presentations that should comprise simple modular approach for each sub-section and a comprehensive model of a business entity.

6. Contextualization: The contextual approach to design and instruct is important. Without a sequential development of instructions and logical reasoning, this is not possible to adhere to the context.
7. Emotional Connection: Besides all these encoding principles, emotional connection of students with the topic from real-world business examples can increase their learning and memorization capability.

Application of Retrieval Principles

1. Space Repetition: I prefer to use weekly quizzes to improve long-term retention of the concepts.
2. Active Recall: For this purpose, I will arrange in-class challenges and peer discussions.
3. Retrieving and Mixed Practice: This practice needs actively recalling materials through smaller activities such as class polls, discussions over single-concept-based vs multi-concept-based problems.
4. Feedback: This important to retrieve feedback on sessions to understand student needs and help them enjoy their learning time.

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Activity 11-1 Collaborative learning:

Harnessing student interactions for deep learning

Activity 1. Reflecting on previous collaborative learning experiences

1. Informal collaborative learning experience

What was the context of the learning?	My wife and I decided to learn how to place an order for items using the drone delivery.
Why it was important for you to learn the knowledge/skills at that time?	<p>Learning this skill is important the way we shop is revolutionizing and purchasing goods and getting it delivered via drone has advantages such as:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced road congestion – Companies are looking into drone technology to do delivery tasks. Lesser delivery trucks or vans on the road will drastically help in reducing the road

	<p>conjunction.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reduced environmental pollution – Delivery drones are known to be more convenient than delivery trucks and are also more efficient. Drones will drastically reduce carbon emission hence protecting the environment to some extent. • Reduced delivery time – Delivery drones carry packages to the desired setpoint without getting affected by road traffic conjunction and on a planned optimized route. Customers will get their delivery in less than 30 mins. • Reduced transportation cost – Drone shipping has several benefits for both businesses and customers. Delivery times are reduced from two to three days, down to a matter of hours, plus there is less chance of a package being damaged during transit and handling as drone flight is smooth.
What did you learn?	We both learnt that we needed to download the appropriate application from Play Store, configure and setup the account, place an order, receive the drone delivery.
What were the processes used in the learning exchange?	Informally, both of us collaboratively (verbally engaged) downloaded the application on to our phones, configured and setup the account, placed an order, received the drone delivery.
Was the learning experience a positive or negative one? Why?	The learning experience was a positive one as we both engaged in a relaxed environment at home, verbally engaged with each other, shared each other's experiences and learnt from each other as well.

2. Formal collaborative learning experience

What was the context of the learning?	Mental Health First Aid Course
Why it was important for you to learn the knowledge/skills at that time?	Each year 1 in 5 Australians will experience a mental illness. Many people are not knowledgeable or confident to assist. Physical first aid is accepted and widespread in our community, however, most do not cover mental health problems. Mental Health First Aid (MHFA) teaches people the skills to help someone who they're concerned about.
What did you learn?	Mental Health First Aid (MHFA) courses teach participants how to assist people who are developing a mental health problem, experiencing a worsening of an existing mental health problem or in a mental health crisis, until appropriate professional help is received, or the crisis resolves.
What were the processes used in the learning exchange?	The instructors presented to the participants and provided ample opportunities for group activities (in small groups). The participants had to discuss and present their findings to the rest of the class.

Was the learning experience a positive or negative one? Why?	The learning experience was a positive as everyone got to learn from each other as everyone had different backgrounds, knowledge and skillset. Sometimes I have seen that some people tend to dominate the group discussions and that may lead other people in the group unheard and this may cause them to feel disconnected.
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3. Commonalities and differences

What did the informal and formal collaborative experiences have in common?	The commonalities included, collaboration, collaborative learning, learning with each other's experiences, knowledge sharing, team learning / group learning.
What were the differences?	The difference was the time, place / setting, context and the group dynamics.

4. Comparison of experiences with others

Similarities?	The similarities in this case were group learning, knowledge sharing, team dynamics / group dynamics, learning from others.
Differences?	The difference in this case was the group dynamics, in the informal context, it was my wife and I learning together as part of self-development and in the formal situation, I was in a workplace setting with colleagues from different departments in a work organised training session.

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Activity 11-3 Collaborative learning: Harnessing student interactions for deep learning

Collaborative learning session plan

PRE-DESIGN: Developing a rationale for teaching a session.

<p>Topic/focus of session: What are you teaching?</p> <p>Reference Management using EndNote.</p>
<p>Learning objective(s): What do you want your students to learn?</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Understand how to use EndNote by creating an EndNote Library, entering references into the EndNote Library from Library Search, Scopus, and Google Scholar 2. Import PDF files into EndNote, choose an Output Style, attach a file to a reference, search within the EndNote Library, customize the display window.

3. Create Groups and Smart Groups, cite references in MS Word, format the paper / thesis, change Bibliography Format / Layout, edit in-text citations, synchronize, and share EndNote Library
4. Create and share references using EndNote Online
5. Seeking additional support for EndNote

Activities: What collaborative learning activities do you intend to use? How are these activities likely to contribute to the learning objectives?

I plan to use the write/pair/share approach to create a collaborative learning environment.

This will enable students to work collaboratively during the training session and “buddy up” to learn from the trainer and enable students to work collaboratively during the training session, as the EndNote training session is practice-based.

Materials: What materials and/or equipment will you need to facilitate the activities?

Materials needed for this activity will be A4 sheet paper and pen (provided in class).

COOPERATIVE LEARNING FRAMEWORK

Description: Give an overview of what the session will look like – how the room is set up, what students will be doing, what you will be doing. How will the session begin and end?

Firstly, the EndNote training session’s duration is two hours. During the introduction, students will be informed that the session will be interactive. They can do self-reflection and peer reflection (if they wish to do so).

Secondly, due to the current furniture, computer, multimedia projector and white screen set up , it would be impossible change the room setup, however, the current room setup mimics the traditional lecture theatre, nonetheless with the presenter in the front of the room presenting to the audience (the presenter has the flexibility to walk around the room, if s/he chooses to do so. The students will be seating in rows of.

Thirdly, the presenter will demonstrate all the steps as per the session outline and the students will be required to follow the steps, the Trainer will recap, and the students will have the opportunity to ask the presenter for clarification or they could ask the person sitting next to him / her.

Lastly, the session will begin with the begin with the students introducing the person sitting next to each other with their name and research topic and at the end of the session the students have the option to either reflect on what they have learnt or in pairs peer review each other’s work.

Positive Interdependence: Explain how you will organise the session so that students will have a

sense of “sinking or swimming together.”

When students introduce each other, they will build a connection. They can communicate during the session.

In addition, they can share their experiences.

Interaction: Explain how you will ensure that students will help each other learn and applaud success and efforts.

Since this is a practical learning experience, students sitting next to each other will be able to collaborate with each other and they will have the opportunity to ask the Trainer or each other questions during the learning process.

Individual accountability: Explain how you will set up the groups so that everyone MUST contribute to achieving the goals and experiencing success.

This training session requires students to create their own (individual) EndNote Library thus they must work independently whilst working with the instructions from the Trainer and the training material.

Interpersonal and small group social skills: Explain how you will encourage communication, trust, leadership, decision making, and conflict resolution.

When students introduce each other, they will form a bond during the session, this will enable them to communicate with others and build trust during the training session.

Group processing: Explain how you will provide an opportunity for group members to reflect on how well the group functions and how to function even better the next time.

The students will receive a Training Evaluation Feedback Form at the end of the training session, and they can provide their feedback to the Trainer.

ASSESSMENT FOR LEARNING

Checking for understanding: During the session, how will you know that they are getting it?

I provide the students with the opportunity to ask and clarify. I recap the steps / process to ensure that everyone has followed through. From time to time, I move around the room and provide feedback on students work.

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Module 11: Activity 2. Structuring and scaffolding collaborative learning

Refer again to the *Cooperative learning made easy* guide downloaded for *Activity 1* - this time, *Section 2: CL Basics* (pages 3-6), which articulates:

- five essential building blocks for successful collaborative learning.
- differences in purpose and approach between informal and formal collaborative learning groups; and
- the role of the teacher in collaborative learning.

Read those pages of the document and relate their contents back to your own collaborative learning experiences that you reflected on in *Activity 1* – especially the formal ones. Write down some brief responses to the following prompts.

1. Do you think that the five building blocks were engaged? If so, how did they manifest in the processes? If not, which one/s do you think were missing?
2. What effect do you think such omission/s might have had on the processes and outcomes of the learning experiences?
3. Did the teacher/s generally fulfil the role outlined in the *Collaborative learning made easy* guide?
4. What, if anything, might the teacher/s have done to enrich the collaborative learning experience further?

Share your notes below. Compare your responses with those of others and respond to someone else's comment in relation to number 4 above. Place copies in your ePortfolio.

1. Do you think that the five building blocks were engaged? If so, how did they manifest in the processes? If not, which one/s do you think were missing?

Five building blocks framework presented by David and Roger Johnson (2009) has certain opportunities. However, with the advent of digital era, cooperative learning theorists need to explore and address technological and digital environment challenges.

Opportunities Aligned with Five building blocks

1. Interaction with social learning environment
2. Individual contribution marker for group success
3. Collaboration opportunity in physical environment

4. Development of social skills such as active listening and conflict resolution
5. Collaborative adjustments to match skills with task

Limitations:

Five building block model brings forth few limitations:

1. Digital collaborations such as virtual meetings and conferencing, digital project development, technological skills etc.
2. Emotional learning aspects such as self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy etc.
3. Interaction with real-world scenarios
4. Conflict and power struggles
5. Culture and language barriers
6. Introversion

Recommendations:

On the analysis of the five-building block model and its limitations, I suggest the following extensions:

1. Digital collaboration platforms induction
 2. One to one counselling for developing emotional learning skills
 3. Individual contribution assessment monitoring
 4. Peer feedback evaluation
 5. Observations of social and emotional skills
 6. Developing equitable relationships amongst peers
 7. Identify and supports connections among the culturally and linguistically similar peers
2. What effect do you think such omission/s might have had on the processes and outcomes of the learning experiences?

Such omissions as mentioned above can affect the processes and outcomes of learning experience in the following manner

1. Difficulty in achieving instructional goals
2. Barrier for students to achieve learning outcomes
3. Barriers to essential skills development
4. Isolation from peer-reflection
5. Low self-efficacy and motivation
6. Hinderance in developing communication skills
7. Lack of self-awareness and self-regulation skills
8. Barriers to conflict management skills development
9. Introversion to isolation in learning environment
10. Lack of understanding of cultural diversity, inclusion and language variations
11. Barriers to meeting challenges in multi-dimensional professional environment.

3. Did the teacher/s generally fulfil the role outlined in the *Collaborative learning made easy* guide?

In my opinion, teacher's role has an adequate definition in the Collaborative learning guide. However, how teachers implement in real-world scenarios varies across multiple settings. I can see the following issues in teachers' role accomplishment in practical scenarios:

1. Creation of equitable opportunity environment for learning experience
 2. Assessment and monitoring of groups formation
 3. Limited in-class social skills development exercises
 4. Pre-assessment discussions on how students can reach to the solution
 5. Ensuing active participation from all group members
 6. Feedback during the group consultations
 7. Skills development focus from the learning outcomes
 8. Feedback on individual contributions
 9. Feedback on group engagement and participation
4. What, if anything, might the teacher/s have done to enrich the collaborative learning experience further?

Share your notes below. Compare your responses with those of others and respond to someone else's comment in relation to number 4 above. Place copies in your ePortfolio.

Teachers' Role to Enrich Collaborative Learning Experience

Teachers are trying their best to foster students collaborative learning experience in the following manner

1. Self-efficacy development with opportunities such as presentations, individual contribution marking.
2. Knowledge building for colorations such as digital awareness
3. Structured collaborative approaches such as Group projects, collaborative notetaking, think-pair-share, peers feedback
4. Unstructured collaborative approaches such as role playing, collaborative problem solving, virtual group workspaces
5. Hybrid collaborative approaches such as flipped classroom, online collaboration tools, meetings and conferencing.

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